

1 **The NFKB activating protein-like is an HIV-1 Vpx target.**

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6 We measured total transcription in primary cells to study reactivity to HIV-1 derived viral stimuli. We report
7 here that cells exposed to Vpx-deficient virion failed to activate NKAPL. This appeared to be the primary
8 molecular defect in cells exposed to Vpx-deficient virus. We conclude that *NKAPL* is a HIV-1 Vpx target in
9 human cells.

10 Citations

11 1. Hrecka, K., Hao, C., Gierszewska, M., Swanson, S.K., Kesik-Brodacka, M., Srivastava, S.,
12 Florens, L., Washburn, M.P. and Skowronski, J., 2011. Vpx relieves inhibition of HIV-1 infection of
13 macrophages mediated by the SAMHD1 protein. *Nature*, 474(7353), pp.658-661.

14 GSE125817